

BB lesion development at 11, 14, and 17 d after inoculation on rice cultivars infected with isolate PXO61 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* race 1 at different growth stages. IRRI, 1987.

Plant age (DAS)	Lesion area ^a (%)		
	Group 1 ^b	Group 2 ^c	Group 3 ^d
	<i>11 DAI</i>		
20	79.7– 87.7 a	53.6–55.5 a	0.8– 4.0 a
30	63.8– 69.4 b	33.9–50.4 a	0.7– 3.0 a
40	27.7– 39.8 c	21.4–18.4 b	0.6– 0.9 a
50	12.6– 25.6 cd	8.3– 7.3 b	0.5– 0.6 a
60	10.8– 21.1 cd	6.8– 6.0 b	0.4– 0.5 a
70	8.2– 16.8 d	4.0– 5.0 b	0.4– 0.6 a
80	5.1– 18.2 d	1.0– 3.4 b	1.2–170 a
	<i>14 DAI</i>		
20	96.3– 98.7 a	72.2–85.6 a	1.5– 7.5 a
30	90.1– 92.3 a	47.6–79.3 a	1.0– 6.2 a
40	50.8– 62.7 b	28.4–33.9 b	0.9– 2.1 a
50	27.5– 41.6 bc	12.1–13.3 bc	0.7– 1.6 a
60	20.6– 37.8 c	9.5–11.0 c	0.7– 1.5 a
70	16.5– 30.7 c	6.8– 9.3 c	0.8– 1.4 a
80	11.3– 31.5 c	2.1– 6.4 c	1.9– 3.0 a
	<i>17 DAI</i>		
20	99.1–100 a	82.3–95.5 a	2.5– 12.2 a
30	97.9– 98.1 a	59.1–92.9 a	2.2– 9.8 a
40	90.9– 79.8 ab	36.2–51.2 b	1.3– 3.1 a
50	42.7– 58.0 bc	15.5–20.4 c	1.0– 2.3 a
60	29.7– 50.7 c	12.1–14.8 c	1.0– 2.4 a
70	26.3– 44.1 c	9.4–13.7 c	1.2– 2.3 a
80	19.2– 47.1 c	4.2–11.1 c	2.5– 3.2 a

^aIn a column within an inoculation date, values followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level. ^bTN1, IR24, RP4-2, IR8, Yolle, M23, IR9101, MTU19. ^cZenith, Pae Moku, Banda Merah, Ase Pute Rone, Gankkyi, Pasle Angga, Kauk Hayin, Pyi Daw Aye. ^dKetan Ireng, Warangal Culture 1263, Sankurcha, IR1545, DV85, Makhmal Mehi.

decreased abruptly at 50 DAS, and were less than 5% at 80 DAS. In group 3, lesion area did not exceed 10% even at

20 DAS (see figure).

These results show that even in a susceptible variety, lesion development

Lesion development in 3 rice cultivars differing in resistance to BB and infected with PXO61 of race 1 at different growth stages. IRRI, 1988.

decreases with plant age. Maximum lesion percentage in a susceptible variety such as TN1, IR8, or IR24 seldom reaches more than 50% of leaf area. This suggests that scoring disease by plant age requires different observation periods. Lesion area in most of the cultivars increased when the plants were younger and decreased as the plants became older. □

Resistance of rice genotypes to bacterial blight (BB)

Shen Ying, Huang Shiwen, and Yuan Xiaoping, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRI); and Lu Fuying, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou, China

During 1987, we screened 50 entries for BB resistance under field conditions at Fuyang Experiment Station. Entries were transplanted in 2 rows of 12 hills each at 20- × 20-cm spacing. BB-infected Guang Lu Ai 4 and local susceptible check Yuan Feng Zao were transplanted in 1 row between each entry and around the test plot.

Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. The trial plot was fertilized with 75-37.5-25 kg NPK/ ha. Entries were inoculated from maximum tillering to booting with BB suspension of local predominant isolates collected and

Table 1. Resistance of rice cultivars to 3 isolates of BB 21 d after inoculation. CNRI, China, 1987.

Variety, line	Reaction ^a to isolate			Origin
	CN-X12	CN-X1	CN-X3	
IR20	1	1	1	IRRI
BR285-5-6-6-2	3	3	1	Bangladesh
BR319-1-HR28	3	3	3	Bangladesh
B4075D-PN-13-1	1	1	1	Indonesia
C731067	5	5	3	Taiwan, China
DV85	5	5	3	Bangladesh
IR29295-70-1-1-1-3-1	3	3	3	IRRI
IR33355-39-1-1-3	3	3	3	IRRI
Kalimekri 77-5	3	3	3	Bangladesh
Kogyoko	5	5	3	Japan
RP2151-173-1-8	1	1	1	India
RP2151-21-22	3	0	0	India
RP2151-40-1	3	1	1	India
RTN90-4	3	3	3	India
UPR79-80	5	5	3	India

^aBB evaluated by *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

isolated from naturally infected leaves, adjusted to a concentration of 6 × 10⁸ cells/ml by leaf tip clipping method.

Of 50 entries screened, 15 were

resistant to BB and 27 were moderately resistant (Table 1). BR285-5-6-6-2, B4075D-PN-13-1, RTN904, RP2151-173-1-8, RP2151-21-22, and RP2151-40-

I had good resistance to three isolates of BB as well as good agronomic traits and high yield potential.

Reaction of the Guangdong differentials to different isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* are given in Table 2. On the basis of these reactions, most of the isolates from Fuyang tested so far belong to groups IV, II, and I. Group IV, virulent on China differentials, was often collected from local popularized varieties. BB was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* at 14 and 21 d after inoculation.

Table 2. Virulence of 3 pathotypes of *X. c. pv. oryzae* collected in Fuyang during 1987 on Chinese rice differentials.^a

Isolate	Reaction					Group
	IR26	Nongkeng 57	Zhaiyeqing 8	Baotaiyai	Jinggong 30	
CN-X1	HR	R	MR	S	HS	II
CN-X3	HR	MR	MR	MR	S	I
CN-X12	MR	HS	HS	HS	HS	IV

^a Ratings based on lesion length and mean lesion length for 20 inoculated leaves. SES 0-9 scale. R (resistant) = 1, MR (moderately resistant) = 3, S (susceptible) = 7, HS (highly susceptible) = 9.

For information on ordering IRRI publications, write Communication and Publications Dept., Div. R, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Scoring systems for evaluating rice varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB): scales for different growth stages

A. Baw and T. W. Mew, IRRI

BB lesion development in rice varies by variety and plant growth stage. The scale as well as time of scoring to assess varietal resistance is influenced by plant age. We attempted to formulate a realistic scoring system for BB at different stages of plant growth. Planting and lesion measurement were the same as in the first study.

Our observation showed that lesions on susceptible varieties inoculated at 20 d after sowing (DAS) reached maximum level at 11 d after inoculation (DAI). Inoculation at 30 DAS produced the most lesions at 11-41 DAI; that at 40 DAS, 11-17 DAI; and that at 50 DAS, 17-20 DAI. Actual lesion area, apparent infection rate, and relative area under disease progression curve (ADPC) were analyzed. Final disease ratings and relative ADPCs followed a similar sequence in lesion area. The infection rates, however, did not follow such sequence, compared to actual disease rating or to relative ADPCs.

Final disease ratings and relative ADPCs were further tested to categorize the level of resistance among the test

Table 1. Varietal resistance to PXO61 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, using different scales at 20 DAS. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Leaf area infected (%)		Relative ADPC		SES scale	
	11 DAI	14 DAI	11 DAI	14 DAI	11 DAI	14 DAI
RP4-2	93.60	100.0	0.232	0.390	9	9
TN1	89.10	99.8	0.230	0.383	9	9
59-439 (BII/MAS)	92.53	100.0	0.218	0.378	9	9
6-1	89.13	98.1	0.210	0.365	9	9
IR24	87.70	98.0	0.199	0.355	9	9
Milyang 23	88.60	98.4	0.193	0.352		
CAS209	84.30	99.2	0.193	0.348	9	9
BG94-1	82.63	96.8	0.188	0.340	9	9
Khao Khao Nhay	78.60	90.0	0.186	0.327	9	9
MTU18	78.90	97.7	0.181	0.332	9	9
IR8	77.77	98.7	0.179	0.330	9	9
Yakai	77.87	98.6	0.175	0.327	9	9
Aneira	75.40	92.4	0.169	0.313		9
Binirnal	75.53	98.6	0.166	0.317	9	9
Pyi Daw Aye	75.20	93.9	0.165	0.311	9	9
Kyeearni	80.07	96.0	0.165	0.318	9	9
Zenith	63.10	76.3	0.155	0.274	9	9
ASE Pute Rono	58.17	76.2	0.147	0.259	9	9
Pale Angga	59.57	85.3	0.141	0.266	9	9
Yolle	66.93	91.5	0.139	0.279	9	9
Kauk Hnyin	64.50	90.7	0.137	0.274	9	9
Banda Merah	62.17	78.7	0.136	0.258	9	9
Gaukkyi	51.50	85.9	0.133	0.228	9	9
Ketan Jimbruk	41.30	49.9	0.100	0.176	7	7
Pae Moku	39.60	64.2	0.091	0.183	7	9
Tahun Gembrong	33.53	39.2	0.088	0.143	7	7
Ketan Ireng	20.30	25.5	0.055	0.092	6	7
Meegauk	22.67	32.1	0.055	0.102	5	7
Akundi	17.70	25.0	0.041	0.078	5	5
Warangal Culture 1263	14.80	23.1	0.040	0.072	5	5
Sankurcha	9.07	13.7	0.022	0.041	5	5
IR20	7.33	10.8	0.020	0.035	5	5
IR22	5.83	9.3	0.017	0.029	5	5
DZ78	6.57	13.8	0.013	0.032	5	5
AUS40	5.13	9.0	0.012	0.024	5	5
AUS463	3.60	5.3	0.008	0.016	3	3
IR1545	3.37	4.4	0.008	0.014	3	3
AUS338	3.57	6.3	0.008	0.016	3	5
Makhmal Mehi	1.00	1.8	0.002	0.005	3	3
DV85	0.53	1.2	0.002	0.003	1	3